

A Study of Spiritual Intelligence of Higher secondary school teachers in Relation to Their Teaching Effectiveness

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Abstract— The purpose of this study was to investigate the relationship between teacher effectiveness and spiritual intelligence of secondary school teachers. Teachers of government and public schools are evaluated by their superiors as well as the effectiveness of their teachers. The study found a significant positive relationship between teacher ineffectiveness and mental intelligence when public school teachers rated themselves or their principals. A significant positive relationship was found for public school teachers when they rated themselves, but no relationship was found when they rated themselves. The study also showed that gender does not affect spiritual intelligence and teacher effectiveness. However, the group with high spiritual intelligence shows higher teaching effectiveness than the group with low spiritual intelligence. A descriptive survey method was used for the research purpose. A sample of 200 male and female secondary school teachers working in Meerut district of Uttar Pradesh was selected using random sampling method. The Spiritual Intelligence Self-Report Inventory developed by King (2008) was used to collect data for this study. Analysis an interpretation of this study revealed that spiritual intelligence was not affected by gender, government or educational experience. High school teachers with different levels of education differ significantly in their spiritual intelligence.

Keywords: Spiritual Intelligence, Teacher Effectiveness, Higher Secondary School Teachers.

I. INTRODUCTION

Teaching is a profession. Teachers play a crucial role in shaping the lives of children. Teachers play an important role in an educational institution by imparting knowledge to the student Sanden riching the talents. Teachers are the backbone of the teaching. The future of the entire nation depends on teachers. The roles of teachers are different. Although teachers teach their students, they play an integral role in the development of the students' whole personality and make them confident enough to faceted l problems. The driving force behind a school is its teaching staff. The caliber of teachers determines the future of any nation. Teachers are social engineers who act as catalysts in the socialization and humanization of impressionable minds, manifesting masculine and feminine qualities. Therefore, the potential, quality, qualification, strength of character and virtues of teachers play an important role in the academic level and quality of any educational institution.

Dynamic active learning opens a world of knowledge, information, experience and education. As stated in the report of the International Commission on Education (1996), no reform can succeed without the cooperation and active participation of teachers. As mentioned in NPE (1986), the position of the teacher reflects the socio-cultural atmosphere of the society; it is said that no one can rise above the level of his teachers. Teaching is a process in which knowledge, skills and attitudes are imparted with the aim of bringing about the desired change in the student. An effective teacher is one who consistently achieves his goals, which are either directly or straight related to student education.

In today's turbulent times, spiritual light has become a very important part of our lives. Recognizing the power of spiritual education, many educational committees have stated that spiritual components are necessary for the good development of students. In today's new preview, spiritual awareness has become very useful for teachers. To foster spiritual growth in the classroom, it is important for teachers to understand spirituality. It is true that spirituallightisn ot just something we learn and believe. What we do and why we do it. Sumthty (2007) found a positive relationship between education and academic success. Benjamin et al (1998) discussed the existence and power of spiritual contenting the counseling process and achieving optimal health. Canister 1999) examined the effect.

of teachers' work on spiritual well-being. Adams, Bezner, Drabbs Zambarano, and Steinhardt (2000) examined the relationship between spiritual and psychological practices and health literacy in college students and found that the effect of the lifetime program on self-perceived health was the same. Rachel and Visvam (2013) found a significant relationship between spiritual knowledge, academic performance and teacher effectiveness. They observed that the effectiveness of,teaching depends on the

spiritual knowledge of the teacher.

Spiritual intelligence is the set of skills that people use to apply, embody, and embody spiritual resources, values, and attributes in ways that improve their daily functioning and well-being. Wigglesworth (2012) defines spiritual intelligence as "the ability to act wisely and compassionately while maintaining inner and outer peace regardless of circumstances. Vaughan (2002) described, "Spiritual intelligence meant the ability to deeply understand existential questions and tap into multiple levels of consciousness. Sisk and Torrance (2001),"Spiritual intelligence is the ability to use multisensory approach to problem solving .and learning to listen his inner voice. Spiritual intelligence refers to wisdom and compassion',\understanding and inner peace; love and freedom; depth and breadth of vision. Wolman (2001) defines spiritual intelligence as the human ability to ask ultimate questions about the purpose and experiences of life, creating a seamless connection between each of us and the world in which we live.

II. COMPONENTS OF SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE

Robert Emmons (2000) defined Mental intelligence as "mental adaptive behavior" .Knowledge to facilitate the solving of everyday problems and the achievement of goal. " He proposed five components of mental intelligence:

- **The ability to transcend matter and matter:** it refers to the mind the act of thinking beyond what is seen. It involves a level of deep thinking.
- **The ability to experience higher states of consciousness:** This is basically attention. One area where conscious breathing can be of great importance.
- **The ability to sanctify daily experience:** simplified, it refers to accept in things as they are rather than as they ought to be. It makes one positive and constructive.
- **The ability to use mental resources to solve problems :**Based on your frame in wisdom or trust in the gutted solve problems that do not have priority is what that means.
- **Virtue Ability:** The references here are to be ethical in demonstrate values in action. It seems that the common thread runs through the threads the above aspects are connected.

The fifth possibility was later dropped as it emphasized human behavior rather than capacity, therefore does not meet previously established scientific criteria a for intelligence. There are not oolemma measure his intelligence because he does not believe it can be measured (Emmons, 2009).

III. THE SPIRITUAL INTELLIGENCE SELF-REPORT INVENTORY (SISRI-24)

In the current model, mental intelligence is defined as a set of mental abilities that facilitate awareness, integration and adaptive application of immaterial transcendent aspects of existence, resulting in results such as deep existential reflection, meaning, recognition of transcendence. Control of self and mental states (King, 2008). King, D. B. (2008) proposes four basic skills or abilities of Spiritual intelligence:

Critical Existential Thinking: Ability to think critically about the nature of existence, reality, universe, space, time and other existential/metaphysical issues; also the ability to think about non-existent things in relation to one's own existence one's existence (i.e., from an existential perspective).

Creation of Personal Meaning: The ability to derive personal meaning and purpose from all physical and mental experiences, including the ability to create and master a life purpose.

Transcendental Awareness: The ability to recognize the transcendental dimensions/patterns of self (ie, Transcendent or Transcendent Self),others, and the physical world (eg, non-materialism) in ordinary states of consciousness, accompanied by the ability to recognize one's own. relationship to himself and to the physical.

Conscious State Expansion: The ability to enter and exit higher states of consciousness (such as pure consciousness, cosmic consciousness, oneness and oneness) and other trance states (such as in deep contemplation, meditation, prayer, etc).

IV. TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS

Teacher effectiveness is clearly related to a set of characteristics, the competence, and behaviors of teachers, that lead to the www.ijsssr.com

student's ability to achieve the desired results, ability to solve problems, think critically and become effective citizens. Effective teachers try to motivate and involve all their students in learning just accept that some students don't have this ability to understand things well effective teachers believe that every student has an ability achieve their goals and teachers do everything possible to meet these expectations. The having knowledge and skills is one of the titles of a teacher qualification in contrast, the use of knowledge and skills in the classroom is called teachers activity. I have seen those who study and try to understand the effectiveness of the teacher, one must be able to combine the competence of the teacher and performance of the teacher

Along with the achievement of the goal soft he teacher, that is with the teacher efficiency (Medley,1982).

The word Teacher Effectiveness refers to the evaluation of achievement in the fulfillment of the institutional and other individual tasks of the teacher his position demands. Teacher Effectiveness includes effectiveness of instructional, student and classroom administration strategies; relationships, evaluation, and feedback etc. **According to Collin English Dictionary, Teacher Effectiveness consists of two familiar words "teacher" and "performance."** A Teacher is a person who teaches i.e. transmits or adding knowledge or skills to the student. Efficiency is the excellent result to achieve the expected result' Teacher Efficiency means the optimal level or perfection of expertise and competence teacher or educator productivity.

V. REVIEW OF RELATED LITERATURE

Sethi (2015) conducted a study on "Spiritual Intelligence as Related to Competence" high school teachers". 100 high school teachers from Abhor and Dowel cities were chosen. The results show that the raise significant relationship between mental intelligence and the competence of secondary school teachers, while there was not significant difference in high school mental intelligence and teaching competence teachers by gender, location, and school.

Kaur and Ravinder Pal Singh (2013) explored the topic and citation; Spiritual Intelligence of Future engineers and teachers by gender, location and family State". 92 students were selected from Punjab College of Engineering and Education a sample for data collection. Members of both groups were found to have high mental intelligence apart from the two which are alertness and intelligence. That too demographics were found to have no significant effect on mental intelligence variables such as gender, marital status and location.

Singh and Singh (2011) conducted a study on the effects of meditation The spiritual intelligence of teachers in relation to gender and religion. An experiment was conducted on 152 B.Ed student teachers based on non-randomized experiments control group pretest- posttest design. Data were collected using Spiritual Intelligence scale developed by Dr. Tirath Singh, Arjinder Singh.

Tripathi and Lata (2020) conducted a comparative study to examine the teaching effectiveness of primary school teachers working in government. and a private institution. The results showed that no significant difference was found between Govt. and private teacher educators in terms of teaching effectiveness, but based on their average, it can be said that the teaching effectiveness of private teachers is relatively better than that of the government Teacher trainers. Teaching efficiency Private teachers are relatively less efficient than government. Elementary school teacher educator.

Bala and Bashir (2016) investigated the relationship between teaching effectiveness and work motivation of secondary school teachers. The sample of this study consisted of 200 teachers selected from Kashmir Valley. The result of the study shows that there isa negative significant relationship between teaching performance and work motivation of secondary school teachers.

Goel (2013) conducted a study on teacher effectiveness related to teacher job satisfaction, personality, and mental health. Her 600 school teachers were selected from her three districts of Punjab. Umme Kulsum's Teacher Effectiveness Scale, Meera Dixit's Job Satisfaction Scale, Ashish Kumar Singh and Her Arun Kumar Singh's Differential Personality Inventory, and Pramod Kumar's Mental Health Checklist were used for data collection. The results of the study showed that female teacher effectiveness was significantly higher for teachers in urban schools compared to teachers in rural schools. Teachers with higher job satisfaction were more effective than teachers with lower job satisfaction.

VI. NEED SAND IMPORTANCE OF THE STUDY

Citizens make the country and teachers make the nation. teachers are real nation builders and institutions control everything that makes up a nation strong foundation. Education is basically a stage that forms the foundation of a student's where their character behavior and personality really develop it determines the future direction of the youth. Teachers are an important part

of the Indian education organization. They can effectively develop the mental growth of the students. The integrated future of the country is inevitably linked to its education organization which in rotate depend on the superiority of its teachers. Effective teachers are needed to make sure a good excellence of education and to make sure the success of students in all aspects. For this teacher must have favorable working conditions, relationships with superiors, colleagues, subordinates, students and their parents, a school communication system, and this is only possible if teachers are emotionally balanced and well aware of the ethics of their profession. translation has a fruitful effect on the performance of these teachers. Their fore the researcher conducted a study on three components to find out the effect professional ethics and emotional into Spirituality on teaching performance of higher secondary school teachers.

VII. OBJECTIVES

The following objectives were formulated to do the present study:

- To study the relationship between Teacher Effectiveness and Spiritual Intelligence of Government and Private Secondary School Teachers.
- To study the difference in teacher effectiveness of high level and low level spiritual intelligence groups. To study the gender male and female differences on both the measured variables.

VIII. HYPOTHESES

The following hypotheses were formulated to test the above written objectives:

- There exists no significant relationship between Teacher effectiveness and Spiritual Intelligence of Government and Private Secondary School Teachers.
- There exists no significant difference in Teacher Effectiveness of High and Low Spiritual Intelligence groups.
- There exists no significant gender male and female differences in both the measured variables.

IX. METHODOLOGY

Method: Descriptive survey method was used for this study.

Population: The population constitute all the Higher secondary schools teachers of Meerut.

Sample: The sample for the present Adopting the on probability sampling technique sample of 200 teachers (Male and Female) from Government and Private Secondary Schools (100 from Government Schools and 100 from Private Schools) of Meerut district was selected for the purpose of the present study. The age range of the subjects varies from 40 to 45 years.

X. ASSESSMENT TOOLS

The Spiritual intelligence Self Report Inventory (SISRI) by D.B King (2008).

The Self-Report Inventory of Intellectual Inventory (SISRI) by D.B King (2008). This is a self-report, four-point scale used to assess mental intelligence in The Self-Report Inventory of Intellectual Inventory (SISRI) by D.B King (2008) This is a self-report, four-point scale used to assess mental intelligence in secondary school teachers, which consists of 24 items. Each item is measured on a four-point scale. All items are rated 4,3,2,1. There is no set time limit. The total score of the test is the sum of all points obtained, which is the mental quotient of the subject. A subject who achieves a higher than average mental quotient is classified as a subject with high mental intelligence and vice versa.

XI. TEACHER EFFECTIVENESS SCALE (TES: KULSUM, 2011)

This scale was used to evaluate the performance of secondary school teachers. The TES consists of 60 items representing five dimensions or domains of teacher effectiveness. Test items are graded by step numbers. The number of steps assigned to each item was taken as the teacher effectiveness score for each respondent. Estimates were taken in two ways. The responding teachers rated them in five areas and the respective managers also rated their teachers and their ratings were also taken in the five areas.

XII. STATISTICAL TECHNIQUES

The tools were refined and the principals 'approval was obtained teachers from various secondary schools were asked to www.ijsssr.com

complete the SISRI and TES scales without missing any items. Concerned leaders were also asked to rate their teachers. All tests performed were evaluated according to the instructions of the respective manuals, and statistical measures such as mean, standard deviation, t-test and Pearson's product moment correlation were used to analyze the data.

XIII. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Spiritual Intelligence

To find out the significant differences in Spiritual Intelligence and Teacher Effectiveness between male and female as well as Government and Private higher Secondary School Teachers, “t”-test was applied. The calculated “t”-values (Table 1) for mean scores of Spiritual Intelligence of male and female higher Secondary school Teachers ($t=0.109$).

Table 1: Means, Standard Deviations along with T-Values on Spiritual

Intelligence of Male/Female and Government/Private higher Secondary School Teachers. (Males: N=100; Females: N=100);

Group	N	Mean	SD	T value
Male	100	87.40	10.15	0.109
Female	100	78.80	10.09	
Government School	100	87.90	10.10	0.107
Private School	100	85.81	13.11	

Government Schools: N=100 and Private Schools N=100).

Government and Private higher secondary School Teachers ($t=1.09$) were in significant at 0.05 level. This means that gender and type of school (Government and Private) do no influence on the Spiritual Intelligence of higher secondary school teachers i.e. gender and type of school does not play an essential role in their Spiritual Intelligence. The findings of the current study are in line with Zohar and Marshal (2004) and Amram and Dryers (2007).

Teacher Effectiveness: (Rated By Self)

Ag glance at Table No. 2 confirms that when the mean scores of Teacher Effectiveness (Rated by Self) of male and

Female school teachers were compared “t”-value came out 0.367 which was insignificant. Similarly, when mean scores of

Table 2: Means, Standard Deviations along with T-Values on Teacher Effectiveness (Rated By Self) of Male-Female and Government-Private Secondary School Teachers (Males: N=100; Females: N=100; Government: N=100 and Private: N=100)

Group	N	Mean	SD	T value
Male	100	506.04	65.04	
Female	100	490.25	63.69	370
Government School	100	503.23	62.32	596
Private School	100	497.12	66.56	

Teacher Effectiveness of Government and Private higher secondary School Teachers were compared the “t”-value came out 0.596 which again shows insignificant differences. It clearly indicates that Teacher Effectiveness is neither affected by gender nor by type of school.

Teacher Effectiveness: (Rated By Heads)

When the mean scores of Teacher Effectiveness of male and female secondary school teachers (Rated by Heads) were compared, the “t”-value was found 0.307, indicating insignificant difference, suggesting that the Teacher Effectiveness rated by Heads was not influenced by gender (Table-3). On the other hand, when the mean scores of Teacher Effectiveness of Government and Private higher Secondary School Teachers (Rated by Heads), were compared, the “t”-value was found 3.54,

indicating a significant difference between them at 0.01 level. This suggests that Heads of Private higher Secondary Schools rated their teachers more effective and competent as compared to the teachers of Government Schools. Bray (1998) and Kitaev (1999) also found that teachers in private schools are generally more intelligent and efficient in teaching than teachers in aided schools.

Table3: Means, Standard Deviations along with T-Values on Teacher Effectiveness (Rated By Their Heads) of Male-Female and Government-Private Higher Secondary value

Group	N	Mean	SD	T Significance Level
Male	100	19.77	2.81	0.37
Female	100	19.63	2.72	0.37
Government School	100	20.18	2.70	3.58
Private School	100	18.89	2.48	3.58

High level And Low level Spiritual Intelligence Groups Secondary School Teachers

In the present study High level and Low level Spiritual Intelligence groups of Higher Secondary School Teachers were also compared. It is evident that contrasting groups give clearer picture of differences. The teachers scoring more than mean scores on Spiritual Intelligence were categorized as High level Spiritual Intelligence Group (HSIG) and subjects scoring less than mean scores were categorized as Low level Spiritual Intelligence Group (LSIG).

Table 4: Mean, SD along with "T"-Ratio of Teacher Effectiveness in High Spiritual Intelligence Group (HSIG) and Low Spiritual Intelligence Group (LSIG) of higher

Variable TE(Self)	LSIG		HSIG		T- Ratio 9.08	Significance Level 0.01
	M	SD	M	SD		
	445.08	65.47	558.87	42.74		
TE(Heads)	LSIG		HSIG		T- Ratio 3.11	Significance Level 0.01
	M	SD	M	SD		
	15.75	19.78	19.87	3.60		

Comparing the average teacher effectiveness (self-esteem) of the high and low mental intelligence groups, a "t" value of 9.08 was obtained, indicating a significant difference between the two groups. The group with high mental intelligence (M=558.87) received a higher score for the teacher's effectiveness than the group with low mental intelligence (M=445.08) when they evaluated it themselves. This shows that teachers with high mental intelligence are more effective teachers compared to teachers with low mental intelligence. On the other hand, when comparing the averages of teacher effectiveness (as rated by principals) of high and low IQ groups, the "t" value was 3.11, which was significant. It shows that the group with high mental intelligence (M =19.87) also received more points than the group with low mental intelligence (M =19.78) according to the school principals. Therefore, it can be seen from the above results that teachers with high mental intelligence were considered to be more effective in teaching, based on both themselves and their own head.

This research result is also supported by Dincer (2007), who pointed out that high mental intelligence plays an important role in educating students of all age groups. The outcomes of this study are also consistent with Noble (2001) who suggested that

high spiritual intelligence can promote psychological health and logical behavior. Emmons (2000) and Zohar and Marshall (2000) suggested that spiritual intelligence is a mechanism by which people can improve their overall quality of life. They believed that when we have a high level of spiritual intelligence and are in touch with our wholeness, we tend to develop intelligent and appropriate behavior. When our spiritual hunger level is low, we become caricatures of ourselves. A teacher with high spiritual intelligence can offer guidance to live from the soul level and self-fulfillment both at work and in private life. Teachers have a strong hand in shaping a child's value systems. A teacher with high mental intelligence can develop them into good personalities.

XIV. CORRELATIONAL ANALYSIS

To study the relationship between Spiritual Intelligence and Teacher Effectiveness, Pearson's Product Moment Correlation was applied a significant.

Table5: Relationship between Spiritual Intelligence and Teacher Effectiveness of Secondary Schools

Groups	Correlation Coefficient (Rated by Self)	Correlation Coefficient (Rated by Head)
Gender		
Male	0.69	0.016
Female	0.004	0.005
Types of School		
Government	0.76*	0.45*
Public	0.48*	-0.06

In self-esteem, a positive correlation was found between men's spiritual intelligence and teacher performance ($r=0.69$). Although the correlation does not show a cause-and-effect relationship, the positive relationship between spiritual intelligence and teacher effectiveness indicates that spiritual intelligent men are more effective teachers. Similarly, the correlation coefficient of public-school teachers clearly shows a positive and significant relationship between spiritual intelligence and teachers' self-esteem ($r=0.76$) and administrators' evaluations ($r=0.45$). This means that spiritually intelligent public-school teachers are more effective teachers when they rate both themselves and their leaders. In the case of public-school teachers, there is a positive significant correlation ($r=0.48$) between mental intelligence and teacher effectiveness when they evaluate themselves. That is, spiritually intelligent public-school teachers believe they are more effective teachers based on self-esteem.

XV. CONCLUSIONS

The major findings of the present study are: -

- The Spiritual Intelligence of Higher Secondary School Teachers does not vary significantly when gender (Male/Female) and type of school (Government / Private schools) were taken into consideration.
- The Teacher Effectiveness of Higher Secondary School Teachers does not differ significantly when gender and type of school were taken into account (Rated by Self).
- The Teacher Effectiveness of Higher Secondary School Teachers different significantly when they were rated by their Heads. Mean scores show that Private School Teachers are better according to their Heads.
- The Spiritual Intelligence of Government Higher Secondary School Teachers is positively correlated with Teacher

Effectiveness when rated by self as well as by their Heads. On the other hand, the Spiritual Intelligence of Private Higher Secondary School Teachers positively correlated with Teacher Effectiveness when rated by self only.

- The Spiritual Intelligence of male teachers was positively correlated with Teacher Effectiveness when rated by self.

The “t”-value clearly shows a significant difference in Teacher Effectiveness of High level and Low-level Spiritual Intelligence groups of teachers. Teachers having High level Spiritual Intelligence are more effective than teachers with low level Spiritual Intelligence. Researchers in this field believed that when spiritual intelligence is high, we are in contact with our wholeness and tend to develop intelligent and correct behavior. When our level of spiritual intelligence is low, we become caricatures of our selves. A teacher with high spiritual intelligence can give striations a bout life and self-realization from the soul level both at work and in private life. Teachers have a strong hand in shaping a child's value systems. A teacher who has high mental intelligence can mold them into good personalities.

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